

Research paper

Single and mixture effects of bisphenol A and benzophenone-3 on *in vitro* T helper cell differentiation

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ABSTRACT

Immune homeostasis is key to guarantee that the immune system can elicit effector functions against pathogens and at the same time raise tolerance towards other antigens. A disturbance of this delicate balance may underlie or at least trigger pathologies. Endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are increasingly recognized as risk factors for immune dysregulation. However, the immunotoxic potential of specific EDCs and their mixtures is still poorly understood. Thus, we aimed to investigate the effect of bisphenol A (BPA) and benzophenone-3 (BP-3), alone and in combination, on *in vitro* differentiation of T helper (TH)17 cells and regulatory T (T_{reg}) cells.

Naïve T cells were isolated from mouse lymphoid tissues and differentiated into the respective TH population in the presence of 0.001–10 µM BP-3 and/or 0.01–100 µM BPA. Cell viability, proliferation and the expression of TH lineage specific transcription factors and cytokines was measured by flow cytometry and CBA/ELISA. Moreover, the transcription of hormone receptors as direct targets of EDCs was quantified by RT-PCR.

We found that the highest BPA concentration adversely affected TH cell viability and proliferation. Moreover, the general differentiation potential of both TH populations was not altered in the presence of both EDCs. However, EDC exposure modulated the emergence of TH17 and T_{reg} cell intermediate states. While BPA and BP-3 promoted the development of TH1-like TH17 cells under TH17-differentiating conditions, TH2-like T_{reg} cells occurred under T_{reg} polarization. Interestingly, differential effects could be observed in mixtures of the two tested compounds compared with the individual compounds. Notably, estrogen receptor β expression was decreased under TH17-differentiating conditions in the presence of BPA and BP-3 as mixture. In conclusion, our study provides solid evidence for both, the immune disruptive potential and the existence of cumulative effects of real nature EDC mixtures on T cell *in vitro* differentiation.

1. Introduction

Current estimates suggest that more than 350,000 different substances and substance mixtures have been released into the environment in recent decades [1] - and we know far too little about their health effects. In particular, there is a substantial lack of knowledge regarding the impact of chronic exposure to low, real life levels of different environmental chemicals. Environmental chemicals enter every household through plastic food and beverage packaging, clothing, cosmetics, sunscreens and cleaning products. In addition, chemicals are released in the form of pesticides in agriculture and are present in rivers and ultimately consumed through fishes. Many of these substances are extremely

persistent and accumulate in the environment as well as in different organs and tissues in the human body [2,3].

Endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) are environmental chemicals that perturb the normal function of the endocrine system in multiple species, including humans. They can mimic or suppress the action of hormones at the wrong time and/or in the wrong site of action, leading to a range of health impacts, including developmental and reproductive disorders, neurological system impairments, and metabolic alterations [4–6]. Moreover, EDCs can disturb the crosstalk between the endocrine and immune system [7,8].

Two representative and widely distributed EDCs are benzophenone-3 (BP-3, (2-Hydroxy-4-methoxyphenyl)-phenylmethanone) and bisphenol A (BPA, 4,4'-(propane-2,2-diyl)diphenol) [9,10]. BP-3 is a widely

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Abbreviations

AhR	aryl hydrocarbon receptor
AR	androgen receptor
BPA	bisphenol A
BP-3	benzophenone-3
ER	estrogen receptor
FOXP3	forkhead box protein P3
IFN- γ	interferon gamma
ROR γ t	rar-related orphan receptor gamma
TH17	T helper cell type 17
T _{reg}	regulatory T cell
TNF- α	tumor necrosis factor alpha

used UV-filter and frequently found in sunscreens, personal care products and even clothing [11]. Beside dermal exposure, BP-3 enters the body via the oral route particularly by drinking water since it accumulates in the environment [12]. It has been detected in serum, urine and breast milk of humans worldwide [13–16] and is able to enter the blood circulation after whole-body topical application [17]. BP-3 is an agonist of estrogen but also has anti-androgenic and anti-progestogenic effects [18]. BPA is used in the manufacture of plastics and epoxy resins. It is present in plastic dishes, bottles and toys as well as food packaging and food cans. Despite BPA was restricted or banned from specific products such as baby bottles and thermal paper, the overall global production is still increasing [19]. Moreover, their substitutes do not appear to be less problematic [20]. BPA is detected ubiquitously in human serum, urine and even amniotic fluid and breast milk [21]. It can interfere with the endocrine system by binding to estrogen receptors (ER) [22,23] and the androgen receptor (AR) [24]. Results from numerous epidemiological studies provide evidence that exposure to bisphenols early in life can lead to increased risk of developing asthma and allergic diseases [25].

With regard to the immune-modulating potential of EDCs it is worth mentioning that immune cells are equipped with several hormone receptors which cause the vulnerability of these cells to EDCs. Particularly, T cells express a variety of hormone receptors such as the ER α , ER β and the AR [26,27] and signalling through these receptors after binding to EDCs may interfere with the numbers and functionality of certain T cell populations.

One major T cell population which is massively involved in the establishment and maintenance of immune homeostasis is represented by CD4⁺ T helper (TH) cells [28]. Upon activation, naive T cells differentiate into distinct TH subsets which express characteristic master transcription factors and lineage-specific cytokines (Fig. 1A). For instance, after encountering viruses, certain antigens or cellular debris,

naive T cells differentiate into TH1 cells, which express the signature transcription factor T-bet and secrete IFN- γ and TNF- α [29,30]. TH2 cells function against extracellular parasites through secretion of cytokines including IL-4, IL-5 and IL-13 [30]. The master transcription factor of TH2 cells is GATA3 [31] (Fig. 1A). In vitro, naive T cells can be driven into TH1 or TH2 cells by adding IL-12 and IFN- γ or IL-4, respectively, into the culture system [32]. TH17 cells fight against fungi and extracellular bacteria. Their differentiation is regulated by the transcription factor ROR γ t and they secrete IL-17 [33] (Fig. 1A). In vitro, TH17 differentiation can be achieved by providing a cytokine cocktail including IL-1 β , IL-6, IL-23 and TGF- β [32]. Another major TH type is represented by regulatory T (T_{reg}) cells. This TH subpopulation suppresses immune reactions after elimination of pathogens and thus prevents excessive immune responses and autoimmunity. Numerous processes on their way to T_{reg} cells are regulated by the transcription factor FOXP3 [34]. After differentiation induced by IL-2 and TGF- β [32], they are important in secreting the anti-inflammatory cytokines IL-10 and IL-35 [35] (Fig. 1A). It is worth mentioning that a particular TH subset is currently not considered a final endpoint [36]. TH subsets are able to adapt to an altered environment and change their phenotype. Consequently, repolarization and the occurrence of intermediate states are natural phenomena [37] (Fig. 1B). Transcriptional factors – also lineage-unspecific candidates – at least partially orchestrate this fine tuning processes [38].

The central task of the immune system is keeping the homeostasis between defence and tolerance. To this end, pro-inflammatory and anti-inflammatory immune responses must be well-balanced, since a disruption of this delicate equilibrium can lead to immune-related disorders such as infections, autoimmunity, atopy, and cancer. It is well known that environmental factors such as nutrition, exercise, stress, and smoking can have an important influence on immune homeostasis [39–41]. Notably, at cellular levels, BP-3 has already been shown to augment TH2 differentiation and suppress TH1 development [42] and TH17 cells seem to be target of the immunotoxic effects of BPA as shown by several *in vivo* and *in vitro* studies [43,44].

Based on this knowledge, the two main aims of our current study was (1) to improve our understanding of potential effects of BP-3 and BPA on TH17 and T_{reg} differentiation and (2) to elaborate on potential differences in single versus mixture effects of these two compounds. Therefore, we studied the potential effects of naive T cells to differentiate into TH17 and T_{reg} cells after single and combined exposure to BP-3 and BPA *in vitro*. We feel that further research is needed to improve our understanding of chemical risk in multi-exposure situations as human beings and other species are constantly exposed to chemical mixtures instead of individual substances. Particularly, we have to pay more attention to whether different compounds enhance or lower each other's biological effects.

Fig. 1. Schematic overview about differentiation pathways into different TH subsets and TH plasticity. (A) TH differentiation pathways including cytokines (green) for achieving a certain TH subset *in vitro* and subset specific cytokine production (black) as well as subset specific functions. (B) TH plasticity displaying possible intermediate states detectable during repolarization from one TH subset to another. Created with [BioRender.com](https://www.biorender.com).

Fig. 2. Study design. Created with [BioRender.com](https://www.biorender.com).

2. Material and methods

2.1. Animals

Animal housing, treatments and experiments conducted as part of this study were approved by the German local authorities (Landesdirektion Sachsen, Germany, T02/21). All experiments were conducted by authorized persons according to the Guide for Care and Use of Animals in Agriculture, Research and Teaching. Female C57BL/6 mice at the age of 6 weeks were purchased from Janvier Labs (Le Genest-Saint-Isle, France) and housed at 23 ± 1 °C on a 12-h light/dark cycle under specific pathogen-free (SPF) conditions at the animal facility of the Saxonian Incubator for Clinical Translation, University of Leipzig. Mice had *ad libitum* access to water and a standard chow (#V1534-300, sniff) and were adapted to the facility for at least one week prior to experiments.

2.2. Chemicals and dose selection

BPA (#239658, Sigma Aldrich, purity ≥ 99 %, CAS number: 80-05-7) and BP-3 (#H36206, Sigma Aldrich, purity 98 %, CAS number: 131-57-7) were solved in ethanol (#5054.1, Carl Roth, purity ≥ 99.5 %). Ethanol was used as a vehicle control in all experiments. The reported human serum concentration of BP-3 varies from values around 0.14 ng/mL (chronic exposure, equals 0.001 μM [16] and more than 200 ng/mL (after application of BP-3 containing products, equals around 1 μM [17]). In the present study, a range of 0.001–10 μM BP-3 was used to mimic human exposure. Similarly, the concentration of BPA was selected according to human serum levels (about 3 ng/mL, equals 0.01 μM [15,21,45]) and urine levels (up to 170 ng/mL, equals around 0.75 μM [46]). The overall experimental design is shown in Fig. 2.

2.3. Isolation and *in vitro* differentiation of naive CD4^+ T cells

Female C57BL/6 mice at the age of 8–12 weeks were sacrificed by cervical dislocation and spleen and lymph nodes were harvested and mixed. For preparation of single cell suspensions organs were pulped through a 30 μm cell strainer. Naive CD4^+ T lymphocytes were purified from cell suspensions using the MojoSort™ mouse CD4^+ naive T cell isolation kit (#480040, BioLegend). Using this kit, naive CD4^+ T cells are separated from all other immune cells by specific labeling of non-naive CD4^+ T cells with biotin-bound antibodies and magnetic streptavidin nanobeads. Subsequently, magnetically labeled cells are retained in a magnetic separator while untouched naive CD4^+ T cells can be collected in the flow-through. Briefly, cells were centrifuged at $300\times g$ for 5 min, and resuspended in an appropriate volume of MojoSort™ Buffer depending on cell number (100 μl is recommended for 10^7 cells). Then,

10 μl of pre-diluted biotin-antibody cocktail was added, mixed and cells were incubated on ice for 15 min. Afterwards, 10 μl of pre-diluted streptavidin nanobeads were added, mixed and cells were incubated on ice for another 15 min. After incubation, 500 μl of MojoSort™ Buffer were added and cells were given on a pre-washed magnetic separator. By adding two times 3 ml of MojoSort™ Buffer the separator was washed and naive CD4^+ T cells could be collected in the flow-through. The purity of the isolated cells measured by flow cytometry ranged between 90 and 95 %. Cells were cultured at a density of 50,000 cells/well in 200 μl /well RPMI 1640 medium (#21875034, Gibco) supplemented with 50 μM β -mercaptoethanol (#M3148, Sigma Aldrich), 1 x penicillin-streptomycin solution (#L0022, biowest), 10 % fetal calf serum (FCS; #3030-31 Biotech) and 1 x MEM non-essential amino acids solution (11140035, Gibco) in a 96 flat-bottom well-plate. To induce TH17 and T_{reg} cell differentiation, naive T cells were stimulated with plate-bound α -CD3 (#100372, clone 145-2c-11, BioLegend, 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) and soluble α -CD28 (#102132, clone 3751, BioLegend, 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) [47]. For TH17 differentiation only, cells were cultured in the presence of α -IFN- γ (#505858, clone XMG1.2, BioLegend, 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$), α -IL-4 (#504138, clone 11B11, BioLegend, 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$), recombinant mouse IL-6 (#21616, Peprotech, 30 ng/ml), recombinant mouse IL-1 β (#211-11B, Peprotech, 20 ng/ml) and recombinant mouse IL-23 (#1887-ML, R&D, 25 ng/ml) [47]. For T_{reg} differentiation only, cell suspensions were treated with recombinant human TGF- β 1 (#100-21, Peprotech, 15 ng/ml) and recombinant human IL-2 (#200-02, Peprotech, 10 ng/ml) in the presence of α -IFN- γ (#505858, clone XMG1.2, BioLegend, 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) and α -IL-4 (#504138, 11B11, BioLegend, 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) [47]. 24 h after starting the differentiation process, BPA and BP-3 were directly added to the T cell cultures in the indicated concentrations. Ethanol (0.05 %) was used as control. Cells were then cultured for another 72 h in presence of the differentiation cocktails and the chemicals at 37 °C and 5 % CO_2 .

2.4. Flow cytometry

Cells were collected from *in vitro* culture and washed with 1 x PBS/1 % FCS. For staining of surface parameters 100 μl 1 x PBS/1 % FCS containing fixable viability dye (FVD) eFluor™ 506 (eBioscience™, 65-0866-14) and appropriate diluted antibodies (Suppl. Table 1) were added and incubated for 20 min at 4 °C. Cells were washed with 1 x PBS/1 % FCS prior to intracellular staining. For intracellular staining of transcription factors, cells were fixed and permeabilized. After cell surface staining, cells were washed with 1 x PBS and fixed using the FOXP3 fixation/permeabilization kit (#00-5521-00, eBioscience™) for 20 min at 4 °C. After washing with 1 x PBS/1 % FCS and saponin buffer (0.3 % saponin (#47036, Sigma Aldrich), 2 % FCS, 1 x PBS), cells were incubated with antibodies (Suppl. Table 1) diluted in saponin buffer for 20 min at 4 °C or with 20 μl PE mouse anti-Ki67 for 20 min in the dark

Fig. 3. The effect of BPA and BP-3 on cell viability (FVD-negative cells) and proliferation (Ki67-expression) following *in vitro* TH17 differentiation. Naïve T cells were differentiated into TH17 cells for 4 days *in vitro* upon exposure to BPA (0.01–100 μM) and BP-3 (0.001–10 μM). (A) Heat map shows percentage of fixable viability dye (FVD)-negative cells within single cells as values normalized for ethanol control. (B) Heat map shows Ki67-expression (MFI) of $\text{CD4}^+ \text{CD45}^+$ cells as values normalized for ethanol control. Statistical analysis: Friedman test followed by Dunn's multiple comparison test (each condition was compared to ethanol). Each heat map row displays a different mouse representing a separate experiment ($n = 6$). BPA, bisphenol A; BP-3, benzophenone-3; EtOH, ethanol; MFI, median fluorescence intensity.

(#556027, Becton Dickinson (BD)). After further washing with saponin buffer and 1 x PBS/1 % FCS, cells were analysed by flow cytometry. For intracellular cytokine staining, cells were stimulated for 4 h with PMA (#P8139, Sigma Aldrich, 50 ng/ml) and ionomycin (#124222, Thermo Fisher Scientific, 750 ng/ml) in the presence of brefeldin A (#B7651, Sigma Aldrich, 5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$). After cell surface staining, cells were washed with 1x PBS and fixed in 2 % formaldehyde (#CP10.1, Carl Roth) for 30 min at RT. Following a further washing step with 1 x PBS/1 % FCS and saponin buffer, cells were incubated with antibodies (Suppl. Table 1) diluted in 100 μl saponin buffer for 20 min at 4 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Flow cytometric analysis was performed after further washing step with 1 x PBS/1 % FCS using the Attune NxT Flow Cytometer (ThermoFisher) and FCS Express Software 7 (Denovo software). Representative gating strategies are shown in Suppl. Fig. 1.

2.5. Semi-quantitative RT-PCR for hormone receptors

Cells were collected from *in vitro* culture after 96 h of differentiation. RNA was isolated by using the high pure RNA isolation kit (Roche Applied Sciences) according to manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, cells were resuspended in 200 μl PBS and 400 μl lysis/binding Buffer and vortexed for 15 s. Then, samples were given into the upper reservoir of a filter tube placed into a collection tube and the entire filter tube assembly was centrifuged for 15 s at 8000 $\times g$. After centrifugation, the filter tube was removed from the collection tube, the flow through liquid was discarded, and the filter tube was again inserted into the used collection tube. Following, 90 μl DNase incubation buffer, 10 μl DNase I per sample was added onto the glass filter fleece in the upper reservoir of the filter tube. Samples were incubated for 15 min at room temperature. After incubation, 500 μl wash buffer I was added to the upper reservoir of the filter tube assembly and samples were centrifuged for 15 s at 8000 $\times g$. This step was repeated twice. Then, the flow through was discarded and 200 μl wash buffer II were added to the upper reservoir of the filter tube assembly. Samples were centrifuged for 2 min at 13,000 $\times g$ to remove any residual wash buffer. To elute the RNA, 50–100 μl elution buffer were added to the upper reservoir of the filter

tube, the tube assembly was centrifuged for 1 min at 8000 $\times g$ and the microcentrifuge tube finally contained the eluted RNA. The RNA concentration was measured on a NanoDrop spectrophotometer and stored at -80°C . cDNA synthesis was carried out by using ImProm-IITM reverse transcription system (Promega) according to manufacturer's instructions. Briefly, 200–600 ng RNA was transcribed at 42 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 1 h in a reaction mix containing 1 x ImProm-IITM reaction buffer, 1.25 μM random hexamer primer, 1.25 μM oligodT-primer, 20 U recombinant RNasin[®] ribonuclease inhibitor, 0.5 mM dNTP each, 1.5 mM MgCl_2 and 1 μl ImProm-IITM reverse transcriptase. Semi-quantitative PCR for the four genes *ar*, *ahr*, *esr1* and *gapdh* was conducted with BIOTAQTM DNA polymerase (BioCat) and Evagreen (VWR International GmbH) as nucleic stain. For gene expression the following primer pairs were used: *ar*, 5'-aatgagtaccgcatgcacaa-3', 5'-atttttcagcccatcactg-3'; *ahr*, 5'-caatg-cacgttgatttacag-3', 5'-tcgtctcttctcatcctgc-3'; *esr1*, 5'-ctgccaaggagactcgtctac-3', 5'-aaggacaaggcagggtatt-3' and *gapdh*, 5'-agaacatcatcctgcatcc-3', 5'-ggctctcagtgtagcccaag-3'. PCR for *esr2* was conducted with the ESR2 mouse qPCR primer pair and SYBR Green Fast qPCR Mix (Origene). All PCRs were performed on a LightCycler 480 (Roche) with the following cycling conditions: 5 min at 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, followed by 45 cycles of 95 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 20 s, 60 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 s and 72 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 30 s. The $\Delta\Delta\text{Ct}$ method was used to calculate the relative quantity of target DNA using *gapdh* as reference gene and ethanol-treated cells as reference group.

2.6. Cytometric bead array (CBA) and enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) for murine cytokines

Cell supernatants were collected from *in vitro* culture after 96 h of differentiation and stored at -20°C . Concentrations of cytokines related to TH cell responses were quantified by using the LEGENDplexTM MU Th cytokine Panel (12-plex) w/VbP V03 (#741044, BioLegend) and the mouse IL-17 DuoSet ELISA (#DY421, R&D Systems) according to manufacturer's instructions.

Fig. 4. The effect of BPA and BP-3 on transcription factor expression following *in vitro* TH17 differentiation. Naïve T cells were differentiated into TH17 cells for 4 days *in vitro* upon exposure to BPA (0.01–10 μM) and/or BP-3 (0.001–10 μM). (A) Heat map shows intracellular ROR γ t expression (frequency) of CD4⁺ CD45⁺ cells as values normalized for ethanol control. Intracellular expression (MFI) of transcription factors (B) FOXP3, (C) T-bet and (D) GATA3 in ROR γ ⁺ CD4⁺ CD45⁺ cells is shown as values normalized for ethanol control. Statistical analysis: Friedman test followed by Dunn's multiple comparison test (each condition was compared to ethanol). * $p \leq 0.05$; ** $p \leq 0.01$; *** $p \leq 0.001$; **** $p \leq 0.0001$. Each heat map row displays a different mouse representing a separate experiment ($n = 5$ –6). BPA, bisphenol A; BP-3, benzophenone-3; EtOH, ethanol; MFI, median fluorescence intensity.

2.7. Statistical analysis

The data were analysed with GraphPad Prism 9 (GraphPad software, Inc.). Significance was calculated by using the Friedman test followed by Dunn's multiple comparison test. Values less than 0.05 were considered statistically significant.

3. Results

3.1. Effects of BPA and BP-3 on TH17 differentiation of murine naïve T cells

First evidence suggests that BPA may interfere with TH17 differentiation [43,44,48,49]. However, the effect of other EDCs like BP-3 and even more the cumulative effects of different EDCs are poorly understood. In order to shed light on this issue, naïve T cells were differentiated into TH17 cells in the presence of BPA (0.001 μM –100 μM) and/or BP-3 (0.0001 μM –10 μM). Viability (by means of FVD), proliferation (by means of Ki67 expression) and expression of characteristic transcription factors and cytokines were assessed. We observed a decreased percentage of FVD-negative cells (viable cells) and Ki67-expressing cells (proliferating cells) after exposure to the highest concentration of BPA tested (100 μM) in comparison to the control (Fig. 3). More precisely, the

number of FVD-negative cells after exposure to 100 μM BPA in combination to 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1 and 10 μM BP-3 was 0.48-, 0.75-, 0.72-, 0.73- and 0.74-fold lower, respectively, compared to the control (Suppl. Fig. S2B). Ki67 expression after exposure to 100 μM BPA in combination to 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1 and 10 μM BP-3 was 0.44-, 0.69-, 0.55-, 0.72- and 0.82-fold lower, respectively, compared to the control (Suppl. Fig. S2D). Neither BP-3 nor any other BPA concentration had an influence on these cellular parameters. To avoid false interpretation of effects on T cell differentiation due to BPA-driven impairments on cellular fate, we decided to exclude conditions involving 100 μM BPA from further analysis.

Since ROR γ t is the master transcription factor of TH17 cells, its expression was used to determine the general TH17 *in vitro* differentiating potential of naïve T cells in the presence of EDCs. We found that neither BPA nor BP-3 alone affected ROR γ t expression under TH17 differentiating conditions. Likewise, only the mixture of 0.1 μM BPA plus 1 μM BP-3 increased ROR γ t expression (Fig. 4A, Suppl. Fig. S3A). More precisely, we observed a 1.06-fold increase in ROR γ t-expressing cells after exposure to 0.1 μM BPA plus 1 μM BP-3 compared to the control (Suppl. Fig. S4A). We also investigated whether BPA and/or BP-3 modulate the occurrence of intermediate states by affecting the expression of the transcription factors FOXP3 (T_{reg}), GATA3 (TH2) and T-bet (TH1) under TH17 differentiation conditions. In a single-substance

Fig. 5. The effect of BPA and BP-3 on cytokine expression following *in vitro* TH17 differentiation. Naïve T cells were differentiated into TH17 cells under TH17-differentiating conditions for 4 days *in vitro* upon exposure to BPA (0.01–10 μM) and/or BP-3 (0.001–10 μM). (A) Heat map shows intracellular (A) IL-17, (B) IL-10, (C) IFN- γ , (D) IL-4, and (E) TNF α expression (frequency) of CD4 $^+$ CD45 $^+$ cells as values normalized for ethanol control. Statistical analysis: Friedman test followed by Dunn's multiple comparison test (each condition was compared to ethanol). Each heat map row displays a different mouse representing a separate experiment ($n = 5$). BPA, bisphenol A; BP-3, benzophenone-3; EtOH, ethanol.

exposure scenario, only a high concentration of BPA (10 μM) induced the expression of T-bet and GATA3 in TH17 cells (Fig. 4C and D, Suppl. Figs. S3C and D). More precisely, 10 μM BPA increased T-bet and GATA3 expression in ROR γ t + cells by 1.19-fold and 1.08-fold, respectively, compared to the control (Suppl. Figs. S4C and D). By contrast, every condition including BPA in combination with 1 μM and 10 μM BP-3 promoted the expression of T-bet (Fig. 4C, Suppl. Fig. S3C). T-bet expression in ROR γ t + cells was increased by 1.23-; 1.28-; 1.27- and 1.32-fold (1 μM BP-3 plus 0.01 μM ; 0.1 μM ; 1 μM and 10 μM BPA, respectively) and by 1.30-; 1.35-; 1.34- and 1.33-fold (10 μM BP-3 plus 0.01 μM ; 0.1 μM ; 1 μM and 10 μM BPA, respectively) compared to the control (Suppl. Fig. S4C). Notably, no increase in T-bet expression in ROR γ t + cells was observable after single exposure to 1 μM and 10 μM (1.02-fold and 0.95-fold change to control, respectively) (Suppl. Fig. S4C). Similar mixture effects were also seen for the expression of GATA-3 and FOXP-3, but to a lesser extent and only in mixtures involving higher concentrations of both compounds (Fig. 4B–D, Suppl. Figs. S3B and D). In detail, FOXP3 expression in ROR γ t + cells was increased by 1.39-fold (10 μM BP-3 plus 10 μM BPA) compared to the control (Suppl. Fig. S4B) and GATA3 expression in ROR γ t + cells was increased by 1.14-; 1.20- and 1.26-fold (10 μM BP-3 plus 0.1 μM ; 1 μM and 10 μM BPA, respectively) compared to the control (Suppl. Fig. S4D). Notably, we did not observe an elevated FOXP3 expression in ROR γ t + cells after single exposure to 10 μM BP-3 (0.93-fold change to control) or 10 μM BPA (0.95-fold change to control) (Suppl. Fig. S4B).

To analyse effects of BPA and BP-3 on a more functional level, the expression and secretion of several cytokines related to T cell immunology were analysed. We did not find any significant effect of BPA, BP-3 and the mixture of both compounds on cytokine expression and secretion of T cells differentiated under TH17 conditions (Fig. 5, Suppl. Fig. S5, S6 and S7).

EDCs are known to interfere with cellular receptors [24,44,50]. Thus, to address possible mechanisms by which BPA and BP-3 achieve their effects, we measured the expression of ER α , ER β , AR and aryl hydrocarbon receptor (AHR) in TH17 cells after exposure to these compounds. Indeed, the exposure of naïve T cells during TH17 differentiation to the mixture of low concentrations of BP-3 and BPA (0.01 μM each) and to the mixture of low concentrations of BP-3 (0.001 μM) and high concentration of BPA (10 μM) resulted in a 0.48-fold and 0.50-fold decreased *Esr2* expression, respectively (Suppl. Fig. S8B). We found no significant effects on the expression of *Esr1*, *Ar* or *Ahr* (Suppl. Figs. S8A, C, D).

3.2. Effects of BPA and BP-3 on T_{reg} differentiation of murine naïve T cells

For both BPA and BP3, an influence on T_{reg} cells has been suggested [51,52]. Yet, the consequences of the exposure to both compounds in a mixture have not yet been studied. Hence, while differentiating into T_{reg} cells, cells were exposed to BPA (0.001 μM –100 μM), BP-3 (0.0001

Fig. 6. The effect of BPA and BP-3 on cell viability (FVD-negative cells) and proliferation (Ki67 expression) following *in vitro* T_{reg} differentiation. Naïve T cells were differentiated into T_{reg} cells under T_{reg}-differentiating conditions for 4 days *in vitro* upon exposure to BPA (0.01–100 μM) and BP-3 (0.001–10 μM). (A) Heat map shows percentage of fixable viability dye (FVD)-negative cells within single cells as values normalized for ethanol control. (B) Heat map shows Ki67-expression (MFI) of CD4⁺ CD45⁺ cells as values normalized for ethanol control. Statistical analysis: Friedman test followed by Dunn's multiple comparison test (each condition was compared to ethanol). **p* ≤ 0.05; ***p* ≤ 0.01. Each heat map row displays a different mouse representing a separate experiment (n = 5). BPA, bisphenol A; BP-3, benzophenone-3; EtOH, ethanol; MFI, median fluorescence intensity.

μM–10 μM) and mixtures of both compounds, respectively. Viability (by means of FVD), proliferation (by means of Ki67 expression) and expression of characteristic transcription factors and cytokines were assessed. Similar to TH17 cells, percentages of FVD-negative cells (viable cells) and Ki67-expressing cells (proliferating cells) were reduced after exposure to the highest BPA concentration tested (100 μM) in comparison to ethanol control, which was therefore excluded from further experiments (Fig. 6, Suppl. Fig. S9). More precisely, the number of FVD-negative cells after exposure to 100 μM BPA in combination to 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1 and 10 μM BP-3 was 0.44-, 0.47-, 0.50-, 0.45- and 0.43-fold lower, respectively, compared to the control (Suppl. Fig. S9B). Ki67 expression after exposure to 100 μM BPA in combination to 0.001, 0.01, 0.1, 1 and 10 μM BP-3 was 0.13-, 0.10-, 0.15-, 0.13- and 0.11-fold lower, respectively, compared to the control (Suppl. Fig. S9D). Neither BP-3 nor any other BPA concentration adversely affected these cellular parameters. By contrast, Ki67 expression was increased after exposure to 1 μM BP-3 plus 0.1 μM BPA and 10 μM BP-3 plus 0.01 μM BPA by 1.25-fold and 1.22-fold, respectively, when compared to the control (Fig. 6B, Suppl. Figs. 9C and D).

Numerous pathways leading to T_{reg} differentiation are controlled by the transcription factor FOXP3. Therefore, we measured the expression of FOXP3 to disclose general effects of BPA and/or BP-3 on the *in vitro* T_{reg} differentiation potential. The presence of BPA and BP-3 alone during cell culture did not influence the expression of FOXP3 (Fig. 7A, Suppl. Fig. S10A and Fig. S11A). This was also true for the highest BP-3 and BPA concentration tested. Fold change of FOXP3 expression compared to the control was 1.01 for 10 μM BP-3 and 0.99 for 10 μM BPA (Suppl. Fig. S11A). However, the mixture of high concentrations of BP-3 and BPA (10 μM each) reduced FOXP3 expression by 0.97-fold compared to the control (Fig. 7A, Suppl. Fig. S11A). Besides FOXP3 expression, exposure to BPA and BP-3 affected the expression of other transcription factors, predominantly RORγt and GATA3 (Fig. 7B–D, Suppl. Fig. S10B, D and S11B, D). RORγt expression in FOXP3⁺ cells was increased by 1.09-fold after single exposure to 0.1 μM BPA and by 1.27-, 1.33- and 1.29-fold after mixed exposure to 0.1 μM BP-3 plus 0.01 μM BPA, 1 μM BP-3 plus 0.01 μM BPA and 1 μM BP-3 plus 0.1 μM BPA, respectively, compared to the control (Fig. S11B). GATA3 which is critical during TH2 differentiation appeared to be promoted by high

concentrations of BPA alone and also by lower concentrations of BPA in the presence of BP-3 (Fig. 7D, Suppl. Figs. S10D and S11D). More precisely, GATA3 expression in FOXP3⁺ cells was increased by 1.08-fold after single exposure to 10 μM BPA and by 1.25-, 1.25-, 1.34-, 1.22- and 1.24-fold after mixed exposure to 0.1 μM BP-3 plus 10 μM BPA, 1 μM BP-3 plus 1 μM BPA, 10 μM BP-3 plus 0.01 μM BPA, 10 μM BP-3 plus 0.1 μM BPA and 10 μM BP-3 plus 1 μM BPA, respectively, compared to the control (Fig. S11D). No effect of BPA and BP-3 was seen on the expression of T-bet in FOXP3⁺ cells (Fig. 7C, Suppl. Figs. S10C and S11C).

According to increased expression of GATA3 under T_{reg} differentiating conditions, we found that the mixtures of 10 μM BP-3 plus 1 μM or 10 μM BPA increased the expression of IL-4 by 6.56-fold and 9.82-fold when compared to the control (Fig. 8D, Suppl. Fig. S13D). This was not the case, when cells were exposed to 10 μM BP-3 (1.02-fold change to control), 1 μM BPA (0.92-fold change to control) or 10 μM BPA (0.76-fold change to control) alone. In addition, BPA alone (0.01 and 1 μM) and 0.01 μM BPA in combination with 10 μM BP-3 inhibited TNF-α production but this was not statistically significant after normalization (Suppl. Figs. S12E and S13E). The expression of no other cytokine was altered upon exposure to BPA and/or BP-3 (Fig. 8, Suppl. Fig. S12, S13 and S14).

Exposure of naïve T cells during T_{reg} differentiation to BP-3 and BPA did not significantly affect the expression of *Esr1*, *Esr2*, *Ar* and *Ahr* (Suppl. Fig. S15).

4. Discussion

Immune homeostasis means, on the one hand, ensuring immune defence against pathogens and, on the other hand, tolerating harmless antigens and avoiding excessive immune reactions [53]. A disturbance of the delicate balance between pro- and anti-inflammatory responses can lead to adverse health outcomes [54].

Environmental chemicals, especially EDCs, are becoming an increasingly important factor in influencing the immune system. Several human studies found an association between the exposure to EDCs and altered immune parameters [7,8]. Not surprisingly, EDCs are discussed in the context of immune-related diseases such as allergy [25,55],

Fig. 7. The effect of BPA and BP-3 on transcription factor expression following *in vitro* T_{reg} differentiation. Naïve T cells were differentiated into T_{reg} cells under T_{reg}-differentiating conditions for 4 days *in vitro* upon exposure to BPA (0.01–10 μM) and BP-3 (0.001–10 μM). (A) Heat map shows intracellular FOXP3 expression (frequency) of CD4⁺ CD45⁺ cells as values normalized for ethanol control. Intracellular expression (MFI) of transcription factors (B) RORγt, (C) T-bet and (D) GATA3 of FOXP3⁺ CD4⁺ CD45⁺ cells are shown as values normalized for ethanol control. Statistical analysis: Friedman test followed by Dunn's multiple comparison test (each condition was compared to ethanol). *p ≤ 0.05; **p ≤ 0.01. Each heat map row displays a different mouse representing a separate experiment (n = 6). BPA, bisphenol A; BP-3, benzophenone-3; EtOH, ethanol; MFI, median fluorescence intensity.

autoimmunity [56] and even an increased risk for COVID-19 infection [13]. Thus, the immune system is doubtless a target of EDCs. However, specific effects and underlying mechanisms are far from being understood. TH cells are an important pillar of immune homeostasis. Here, we aimed to elucidate the effects of the widely distributed EDCs BPA and BP-3 on TH17 and T_{reg} differentiation, two TH populations that function as a more pro- and an anti-inflammatory TH cell population, respectively.

To this end, we exposed differentiated TH17 and T_{reg} cells to environmentally relevant concentrations of both EDCs alone or in mixtures. We did so using murine cells whose phenotype and functionality are similar to human cells and allow a study design that is better controllable and minimize the different responses in different individuals owing to different cycle phases in women, age, individual predisposition, and many other factors that could make it difficult to interpret the data. Different analytical tools were used to detect effects of chemical exposure at the cellular and molecular levels. For both TH17 and T_{reg} cells, exposure to 100 μM BPA turned out to be toxic independently of BP-3 as measured by decreased cell viability (based on FVD-cells) and proliferation (based on Ki67 expression) (Figs. 3 and 6). However, no other BPA or BP-3 concentration appeared to impair cell viability so we proceeded to study their effect on functional parameters and possible phenotype changes. In fact, lower concentrations of BPA and BP-3 seemed to have a rather proliferative effect on T_{reg} cells (Fig. 6). Various information

regarding the proliferative potential of these EDCs can also be found in the literature but some of them are contradictory. While BPA promoted proliferation of murine splenocytes *in vivo* [57,58] and human peripheral blood mononuclear cells (PBMCs) [59], anti-proliferative effects on human immune cells *in vitro* were reported especially after long-term exposure [60,61]. For BP-3 only a few studies comment on effects on immune cell proliferation. Recently, Morin and colleagues found that 30 μM BP-3 reduced proliferation of murine T_{reg} cells *in vitro* [52]. The duration and concentration of exposure as well as the particular cell type, appear to have crucial effects on the outcome of these studies. Hence, it is currently still difficult to assess the relevance of the effects of EDCs on immune cell proliferation, particularly in living organisms, which requires further investigation.

Besides effects on cell viability and proliferation, EDCs are also known to modulate the phenotype of immune cells [62]. The purpose of this study was to further disclose whether BPA and/or BP-3 affect the differentiation of TH17 and T_{reg} cells. Several *in vitro* and *in vivo* studies suggest that BPA promotes TH17 immunity [43,44,48,49]. In particular developmental exposure to BPA resulted in a dose-related increase of TH17 in mouse spleen [43]. Two studies of Malaise and colleagues further support this assumption [48,49]. Notably, these studies demonstrating the TH17-promoting potential of BPA finally convinced the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) to lower the tolerable daily intake (TDI) by a factor of 20,000 a few months ago [63]. This recent

Fig. 8. The effect of BPA and BP-3 on cytokine expression following *in vitro* T_{reg} differentiation. Naïve T cells were differentiated into T_{reg} cells under T_{reg}-differentiating conditions for 4 days *in vitro* upon exposure to BPA- (0.01–10 μM) and BP-3 (0.001–10 μM). Heat map shows intracellular (A) IL-17, (B) IL-10, (C) IFN-γ, (D) IL-4, and (E) TNF-α expression (frequency) of FOXP3⁺ CD4⁺ CD45⁺ cells as values normalized for ethanol control. Statistical analysis: Friedman test followed by Dunn's multiple comparison test (each condition was compared to ethanol). *p ≤ 0.05. Each heat map row displays a different mouse representing a separate experiment (n = 4–6). BPA, bisphenol A; BP-3, benzophenone-3; EtOH, ethanol.

policy decision clearly shows that even after years and decades, the risk assessment of BPA is not yet completed and needs ongoing scientific clarification as further effects arise that toxicological tests cannot address. This may also apply for other EDCs such as BP-3 whose immunological effects are even less well known. Nevertheless, BP-3 was shown to activate RORγt in a CHO-derived RORγt reporter cell line [64]. Thus, it would stand to reason that both BPA and/or BP-3 promote TH17 differentiation in the present model. By contrast, we did not find a meaningful effect of BPA and/or BP-3 on the expression of RORγt and IL-17 under TH17-polarizing conditions indicating that both EDCs neither inhibit nor promote TH17 cell differentiation (Figs. 4 and 5). The discrepancy between the study results might be caused by model specifications, for example a different exposure time point and duration [44].

In addition to analysing the principal polarization potential of TH17, we also investigated whether EDCs can modulate the expression of other transcription factors than RORγt. It is known that TH cells are in contact with the environment and that a changing environment can induce phenotypic alterations of T cells, i.e. the emergence of intermediate states that exhibit characteristics of different TH subsets [38] (Fig. 1). Here we found that exposure to high concentrations of BPA (10 μM) induced the expression of T-bet in TH cells differentiated under TH17-polarizing conditions, whereas BP-3 alone did not (Fig. 4). However, when TH17 cells were differentiated in the presence of the EDC mixture, even lower BPA concentrations (<10 μM) promoted the expression of T-bet in the presence of BP-3 (>1 μM) (Fig. 4). Together,

these results suggest that BP-3 may enhance weaker effects of BPA at lower concentrations. As our results did not show significant effects on cytokine expression or secretion *in vitro* (Fig. 5), it is unclear whether and what effects on cell functionality arise. Further investigation is needed to clarify this issue in detail. Yet, T-bet was shown to foster the development of a TH1-like TH17 intermediate state meaning TH cells expressing RORγt and T-bet at the same time (Fig. 1). These pro-inflammatory cells produce IFN-γ and play a crucial role in the pathogenesis of colitis [65]. Moreover, TH1-like TH17 cells are associated with other autoimmune diseases including multiple sclerosis, rheumatoid arthritis and primary Sjögren syndrome [66]. By interfering with complete differentiation in TH17 cells and promoting a rather pro-inflammatory TH1-like TH17 intermediate phenotype, BPA and BP-3 might have a negative impact on or even trigger certain autoimmune diseases. Further *in vivo* studies using the respective disease model as well as deep analysis using population cohort studies might help to prove this assumption.

In addition to TH17 cells, we also investigated the effect of BPA and BP-3 on T_{reg} *in vitro* differentiation. Overall, the data about effects of BP-3 on T_{reg} cells is very limited [52]. Knowledge about the influence of BPA on T_{reg} cells is somehow more comprehensive. Like BP-3, BPA seems to have an inhibitory effect on T_{reg} cells. For example, perinatal exposure to BPA resulted in reduced T_{reg} cell numbers in mouse spleen [51,67]. In the present study, only exposure to the EDC-mixture in high concentrations (10 μM each) led to impairment of naïve T cells into T_{reg} cells measured by a reduction of FOXP3 expression (Fig. 7). Since the

Table 1
Overview of studies displaying an effect of BPA and/or BP-3 on T cells.

Effect category	Chemical Name	Species	Exposure administered or measured	Immune Effects	Reference
Proliferation	BPA	human, PBMCs (male)	0.3–30 nM 24 h treatment, cells were cultured for a total of 49 days	– long-term “low-dose” BPA exposure: proliferation ↓, IFN- γ ↓ (CD8+T cells)	[61]
Proliferation	BPA	human, PBMCs (male and female)	1–1000 nM	–long-term “low-dose” BPA exposure: proliferation ↓	[60]
Proliferation	BP-3	mouse	30 μ M	–proliferation ↓ (after <i>in vitro</i> T _{reg} differentiation)	[52]
Immune effect, proliferation	BPA	mouse	3, 30, 300 or 3000 μ g/kg prenatal exposure	–proliferation ↑ (3000 μ g/kg BPA, spleen) –IFN- γ and IL-4 ↑ (spleen) –numbers of CD3 ⁺ , CD4 ⁺ and CD8 ⁺ cells ↑ (spleen)	[57]
Immune effect, proliferation	BPA	human, PBMCs	0.1 and 1 nM	–proliferation ↑ (after stimulation) –IL-10 and IL-13 ↓	[59]
Proliferation, viability	BPA and BP-3	mouse, <i>in vitro</i> TH17 and T _{reg} differentiation	0.01–100 μ M BPA and/or 0.001–10 μ M BP-3	–no proliferation effect in TH17 cells –proliferation in T _{reg} cells ↑ (1 μ M BP-3 + 0.1 μ M BPA and 10 μ M BP-3 + 0.01 μ M BPA) –viability in TH17 and T _{reg} ↓ (100 μ M BPA)	present study
Immune effect	BPA	mouse	50 μ g/kg body weight/day perinatal	–TH1 and TH17 ↑ (spleen) and (small intestinal lamina propria (siLP)) ↓	[48]
Immune effect	BPA	mouse	50 μ g/kg body weight/day perinatal	–activated and regulatory T cells (siLP) ↓ –TH17, IFN- γ and IL-17 ↑ (siLP) –TH17 and IL-17 ↑ (spleen) T _{reg} ↓ (siLP and spleen)	[49]
Immune effect	BPA	mouse, human	0.05 to 50,000 nM	–TH17 differentiation ↑ (5 nM BPA) and ↓ (500 and 50,000 nM; naïve murine CD4 ⁺ T cells) –IL-17 and IL23 ↑ (0.05 nM, mouse spleen and siLP) –IL-17 and IL23 ↓ (50,000 nM, human CD4+T lymphocytes) –mechanism might involve an AhR-dependent pathway	[44]
Immune effect	BPA	mouse, male	0.2 or 2.0 μ g/ml drinking water perinatal	–IL-17, TNF- α ↑ and IFN- γ ↓ (serum) –TH17 ↑ and T _{reg} ↓ cell (spleen) –FOXP3 ↓ and ROR γ t protein expression ↑ (spleen) –ER α , AhR, TLR4, and NF- κ B protein expression ↑ (spleen)	[51]
Immune effect	BPA	mouse, female	0.2 or 2.0 μ g/ml drinking water perinatal	–TH17 ↑ and T _{reg} ↓ cell (spleen) –FOXP3 ↓ and ROR γ t protein expression ↑ (spleen) –AhR protein expression ↑ (2.0 μ g/ml, spleen)	[67]
Immune effect	BPA	mouse	10, 100 or 1000 nM, perinatal exposure	–TH17 ↑ (spleen) –IL-17, IL-21 IL-6 and IL-23 ↑ (serum) –ROR γ t mRNA expression ↑ (spleen) –dose-dependent, gender-specific effects	[43]
Immune effect	BPA	mouse	0.015, 1.5 and 30 mg/ml in drinking water for 4 weeks	–IFN- γ ↑ and IL-4 ↓ (spleen) –transcription of IRF-1 (Th1) ↑ and of GATA-3 (TH2) ↓ (spleen) –splenocyte proliferation in response to Con A ↑ (spleen, all tested concentrations) –ROR γ t activity ↑	[58]
Immune effect	BP-3	hamster, CHO cells	10 μ M	–ROR γ t activity ↑	[64]
Immune effect	BPA and BP-3	mouse, <i>in vitro</i> TH17 and T _{reg} differentiation	0.01–100 μ M BPA and/or 0.001–10 μ M BP-3	–only slight effect on TH17 differentiation –expression of T-bet and GATA3 under TH17 differentiation condition ↑ (mixtures of BPA and BP-3) –only slight effect on T _{reg} differentiation –expression of ROR γ t and GATA3 under T _{reg} differentiation condition ↑ (mixtures of BPA and BP-3)	present study
Immune effect	BP	mouse	0.001–100 μ M	–IL-4 (TH2) ↑ and IFN- γ (TH1) ↓ (spleen)	[42]
Mechanistic effect	BPA	human, HeLa9903 cells	100 pM–100 μ M	–ER α activity ↑, AR activity ↓ –AhR-mediated activity (10 μ M)	[24]
Mechanistic effect	BP-3	human, HEK293 and U2-OS cells	various	–estrogenic activity –antagonistic towards androgene and progesterone receptor	[18]
Mechanistic effect	BPA	human, Ishikawa, HeLa, and HepG2	1, 10, 100, or 1000 nM	–estrogenic activity is cell line and concentration-dependent	[22]
Mechanistic effect	BPA and BP-3	mouse, <i>in vitro</i> TH17 and T _{reg} differentiation	0.01–100 μ M BPA and/or 0.001–10 μ M BP-3	–ER β expression (TH17 cells) ↓	present study

individual substances had no effects at the same concentration (Fig. 7), we assume additive effects which again provides evidence for the existence of mixture effects. The further analysis of transcription factors that are co-expressed under T_{reg} cell differentiating conditions, revealed an effect of BPA and BP-3 on GATA3 expression (Fig. 7). Both EDCs seem to enhance each other’s biological effect, meaning that even low concentrations induce an increase in GATA3 expression, which is not predictable from the observations after exposure to individual compounds (Fig. 7). The development of a so-called TH2-like T_{reg} intermediate state

characterized by parallel expression of FOXP3 and GATA3 (Fig. 1) after exposure to EDCs was further supported by measuring elevated IL-4 expression (Fig. 8). This suggests not only transcriptional alterations but also consequences for the function of this TH2-like T_{reg} cell subpopulation. This specific TH subpopulation has been associated with the pathogenesis of food allergy [68] and atopic dermatitis [69]. Also a role in supporting a tumour-promoting environment is already being discussed [70]. Based on the results of the present study, we can only speculate that the increased expression of GATA3 and IL-4 *in vitro*

differentiated T_{reg} cells is an indication of potentially adverse health effects of BPA and BP-3. This could be a relevant starting point for ongoing studies.

To get insight into potential mechanisms underlying the effects of BPA and BP-3 on T cell differentiation, we investigated their influence on expression of specific hormone receptors that have been discussed as targets of EDCs including ER α , ER β , AR and AHR [24,44,50]. All these receptors regulate multiple aspects of T cell immunology. For instance, testosterone increased the expression of FOXP3 in T_{reg} cells via the AR *in vitro* and also promoted T_{reg} expansion in mice [27,71]. Moreover, ER α was shown to support pro-inflammatory function of T cells as well as T cell activation and proliferation [72,73]. Specifically during TH17 differentiation, ER α facilitates the production of IL-17. Hence, deletion of ER α in T cells ameliorated symptoms in certain models of disease, such as T-cell dependent colitis and dermatitis [73]. The variety of processes regulated by these receptors accounts for the broad spectrum of potential consequences of exposure to EDCs such as BPA and BP-3. Here, we found that selected mixtures of BPA and BP-3 inhibited the expression of ER β during TH17 differentiation (Suppl. Fig. S8B). In T cells, ER β appears to play a more anti-inflammatory and thus opposite role to ER α . The activation of this receptor in CD4⁺ T cells suppressed TH17 expansion and promoted T_{reg} differentiation [74]. Accordingly, a protective effect of this receptor is discussed in inflammatory bowel disease, systemic lupus erythematosus and a model of spontaneous chronic myeloid leukaemia [75–78]. Unfortunately, the results of the present study do not directly predict the importance of decreased ER β expression for TH17 cell differentiation and function, but they may be a worthwhile starting point for future studies. In particular, it should be further investigated whether the decrease in ER β expression might be related to a more pro-inflammatory phenotype of TH17 cells. The observations of ER β expression made here are again evidence of the occurrence of cumulative effects after exposure to EDC mixtures. In comparison to the mixture of BPA and BP-3, the individual substances did not affect the expression of the hormone receptor (Suppl. Fig. S8B). We suggest that more attention should be paid to chemical mixtures when designing studies that address health effects of EDCs, especially since humans are never exposed to individual compounds in the natural environment. Remarkably, there was no effect on the expression of other cellular receptors in TH17 cells measured in the present study nor any alterations of the receptor expression in T_{reg} cells ((Suppl. Figs. S8 and S15). However, it would be too early to conclude that these receptors do not play any role in the observed changes in TH17 and T_{reg} differentiation. BPA and BP-3 can also directly bind to receptors, thus directly mimicking the function of endogenous hormones and ligands and induce agonistic or antagonistic effects [18,22,24]. The use of specific receptor inhibitors or mouse models with T cell-specific knockdown of these receptors, could further elucidate these mechanisms. In addition to receptor-mediated effects, EDCs were shown to induce epigenetic and oxidative stress, which may also result in altered immune cell functions [7]. We have only begun to understand how EDCs may impact T cell differentiation. To find out, all these pathways need to be considered in future studies.

A limitation of our study is the sole usage of naïve T cells from female mice for the analyses. It has long been noticed that sex correlates with differences in immunological responses [79]. We did so because we are interested in the impact of EDCs on female health and fertility. However, it would be of interest to follow up by studying potential differences between male and female regarding impact to EDC exposure at immune cell level. Indeed, there are already studies that point towards different effects of EDCs in males and females [43,51]. For instance, Luo and colleagues found that the increased TH17 frequency in spleen after perinatal exposure to BPA was more profound in female than in male offspring [43]. Thus, it would be worth investigating in the future whether exposure to BPA and BP-3 lead to different outcomes in male naïve T cells differentiated according to the model presented here.

In conclusion, the present study shows that exposure of BPA and BP-3

influenced the *in vitro* differentiation of murine naïve T cells. The development of TH1-like TH17 and TH2-like T_{reg} intermediate states was particularly favoured in the presence of the mixture of both EDCs compared with the individual substances. This observation is not only an indication that BPA and BP-3 have immune-dysregulating functions but also provide evidence for the existence of combined effects of different EDCs on T cells (summarized in Table 1). This aspect is not only relevant for *in vitro* studies, but should also be considered more in the experimental design of *in vivo* studies, as it reflects the real exposure in our natural environment.

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CRediT authorship contribution statement

Florence Fischer: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Miriam Rebecca Ermer:** Investigation. **Julia Howanski:** Investigation. **Ziran Yin:** Investigation. **Mario Bauer:** Methodology. **Marita Wagner:** Investigation. **Beate Fink:** Investigation. **Ana C. Zenclussen:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Anne Schumacher:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cbi.2024.111011>.

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